

Investigating Artificial Intelligence Potentials for Mathematical Innovation and Discovery among Adeyemi College of Education students in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was based on exploring the potentials of artificial intelligence for mathematical creativity and discovery. Five research questions were posed and five hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study was carried out in Adeyemi College of Education. The sample used for the study was 285 students. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions, while the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was adopted in testing the hypotheses at $P < 0.05$ probability level. The findings of the study reveal that artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to transform the field of mathematics by helping researchers to make creative and innovative discoveries. The findings suggest that artificial intelligence (AI) has the potentials to generate new mathematical theorems, proofs, and conjectures. Additionally, AI can be used to identify new patterns and structures in mathematical research and problem-solving. The project used a combination of AI techniques, including machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing, to analyze and generate mathematical content. By doing so, the project aims to advance the state of the art in AI and mathematics.

Keyword: Artificial intelligence, Mathematical creativity, Discovery, deep learning, mathematical theorems, AI techniques.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) applications in education are becoming more popular and have gotten a lot of press in recent years. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a leap across creative and innovative thinking in various fields, including mathematics education. The field of mathematics has a rich history of creativity and discovery, where mathematicians have pushed the boundaries of knowledge through novel insights, theorems, and conjectures. With the emergence of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, there is growing interest in exploring how artificial intelligence (AI) can complement and enhance human mathematical creativity and aid in the process of mathematical discovery. This field represents an interdisciplinary convergence of mathematics, computer science, and cognitive science, aiming to leverage AI to tackle complex mathematical problems, propose new conjectures, and foster innovative exploration.

The study involves investigating how artificial intelligence (AI) can contribute to generating novel mathematical ideas, solving complex mathematical problems, and fostering creative exploration in mathematics. Researchers aim to develop AI algorithms that can mimic human-like mathematical thinking, propose new conjectures, and explore uncharted mathematical territories, ultimately pushing the boundaries of mathematical knowledge through computational assistance. This interdisciplinary field merges concepts from mathematics, computer science, and AI, aiming to uncover new mathematical insights through the collaboration between humans and machines. The work of some researchers like (Chen et al., 2020a; Cope et al., 2020; He et al., 2019; Schiff, 2021; Vaishya et al., 2020) show the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) to mathematics, education and the world at large for example the use of AI enhance our abilities in living a life covered in increasingly sophisticated technology. According to Gao (2020), based on the development of computer technology, AI continues to expand and innovate. Artificial intelligence (AI) enables students to develop and enhance more mathematical skills and cognitive skills in learning. Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) present an overview of this research. They identify four major directions of current research in the area of AI in education. These are: Profiling and prediction, assessment and evaluation, adaptive systems and personalization, intelligent tutoring systems. Intelligent tutoring systems (ITS), which include the AI assistant we develop, are systems in which one-to-one personal tutoring takes place, where the role of the teacher is fully represented by a computer system. The first major research direction they highlight is "Profiling and Prediction." This involves the use of AI to analyze data and create profiles of learners based on their behaviors, interactions, and learning patterns. These profiles can then

be utilized to predict learners' preferences, needs, and performance outcomes. By understanding individual students better, educators and AI systems can tailor learning experiences and interventions to suit their specific requirements. The second research direction is "Assessment and Evaluation." This area delves into how artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance the assessment process by automating grading, providing feedback, and even predicting learners' future performance. AI-driven assessment tools can efficiently analyze and evaluate large volumes of student work, freeing up educators' time and providing timely insights to learners for improvement. The third focus area identified by Zawacki-Richter et al. is "Adaptive Systems and Personalization." Here, Artificial intelligence (AI) is leveraged to create adaptive learning environments that adjust content, resources, and challenges based on each learner's progress and individual learning pace. This approach aims to provide personalized learning pathways that optimize engagement and comprehension.

Attard (2021) in his research conducted a findings focusing on explaining the knowledge from mathematics, according to which 73% of the users enjoyed making use of the chatbot, and the same percentage of respondents also expressed a desire to use the chatbot again in the future. According to the study, a significant percentage of users, specifically 73%, reported enjoying their interactions with the chatbot. This positive response implies that users found the chatbot's assistance valuable, engaging, and helpful when it came to dealing with mathematical concepts and problems. Interestingly, the same percentage of respondents, that is, 73%, expressed a desire to use the chatbot again in the future. This observation underscores the potential long-term appeal and utility of the chatbot as an educational aid for mathematics. The fact that such a substantial portion of participants is interested in continuing to utilize the chatbot indicates that they see a practical benefit in its assistance.

Grohs et al (2022) work provides an in-depth exploration of the mathematical foundations underlying deep learning techniques. It investigates the intricate mathematical structures that form the basis of deep learning algorithms, offering readers a comprehensive understanding of the theoretical underpinnings of this cutting-edge technology. The work emphasizes the role of mathematics in shaping the field of deep learning, focusing on intricate topics such as high-dimensional geometry, optimization theory, and statistical learning theory. By unraveling the complex mathematical structures behind deep learning algorithms, the book equips readers with the knowledge to analyze, interpret, and enhance the performance of deep learning models. It bridges the gap between theoretical mathematics and practical machine learning applications, catering to both mathematicians interested in applied areas and machine learning practitioners seeking a deeper understanding of the underlying mathematical principles. It serves as a comprehensive guide that illuminates the mathematical intricacies of deep learning. It provides readers with a profound insight into the mathematical foundations of deep learning algorithms, empowering them to navigate the complex landscape of modern machine learning techniques with a solid mathematical understanding.

Ginsburg (1996) research shows the connection to the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the realm of mathematics. In traditional mathematics education and problem-solving, the focus has often been on arriving at accurate solutions. However, the essence of mathematics extends beyond mere correctness. It involves the ability to approach problems from various angles, devise innovative strategies, and explore novel approaches to arriving at solutions. Creative thinking in mathematics encourages the exploration of patterns, connections, and insights that might not be immediately evident. When we consider the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in mathematics, we find that AI systems can complement and enhance this creative aspect of mathematical thinking. AI algorithms, particularly those related to machine learning and pattern recognition, can process vast amounts of data and generate insights that might elude human observers. Artificial intelligence (AI) can identify intricate relationships, detect subtle patterns, and provide fresh perspectives on mathematical problems. In essence, Artificial intelligence (AI) amplifies the creative potential of mathematics by providing innovative approaches, unveiling hidden relationships, and encouraging mathematicians to explore the depths of mathematical discovery beyond the realm of rote calculation. By synergistically combining the capabilities of artificial intelligence (AI) and human creativity, we embrace the true essence of mathematics—creative thinking that transcends the boundaries of mere correctness.

Wu (2021) research paper explores the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in the realm of mathematics education, particularly in the teaching of basic mathematical concepts. While the primary focus of the paper is on enhancing math instruction, several key aspects of the research relate to mathematical creativity and discovery.

1. **AI-Powered Visualization:** The research employs AI-driven visualization tools to aid in the teaching of basic mathematics. These visualizations go beyond traditional teaching methods, offering interactive and dynamic representations of mathematical concepts.
2. **Enhancing Creativity:** By providing students with interactive and visually stimulating content, AI-driven visualizations encourage creative thinking in mathematics. Students are prompted to explore mathematical ideas in innovative and engaging ways.

3. **Personalized Learning:** AI in mathematics education often embraces personalized learning techniques. This means that the content and challenges are tailored to individual students' needs and abilities. This personalized approach allows students to delve deeper into mathematical concepts, potentially leading to new discoveries.

Objectives of the study

Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine how AI can contribute to the generation of innovative mathematical ideas and concepts. By investigating AI algorithms' ability to propose new conjectures, explore uncharted mathematical territories, and provide fresh perspectives, the research aims to uncover the extent to which AI can stimulate and augment human creative thinking in mathematics.
2. Assess how AI technologies can streamline the process of mathematical discovery. By harnessing AI's computational power, researchers intend to explore ways to automate complex calculations, verify conjectures, and systematically navigate vast mathematical solution spaces. This could potentially lead to faster insights and solutions in challenging mathematical problems.
3. Examine the Ethical and Philosophical Implications of AI's in mathematical creativity: Ethical considerations surrounding AI's role in mathematical creativity are paramount. The study aims to delve into the ethical dimensions of AI-generated mathematical insights, including questions of authorship, attribution, and the impact of machine-generated ideas on the essence of human creativity. By examining these aspects, the research seeks to contribute to ethical guidelines for integrating AI into mathematical exploration.
4. Identify the practical applications of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery across diverse fields, including optimization, data analysis, and scientific modeling.
5. Investigate the strategies for optimizing collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems to maximize creativity synergy.

Research Questions:

The following Research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent can artificial intelligence algorithms simulate human-like innovative in proposing new mathematical conjectures and exploring uncharted problem domains?
2. To what extent can artificial intelligence automate complex calculations, verify mathematical conjectures, and assist human mathematics in solving challenging problems?
3. How do the ethical considerations and philosophical implications of integrating AI-generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity influence the attributions of mathematical discoveries and creativity?
4. What are the potential practical applications of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery, particularly in fields like cryptography, optimizations, data analysis and scientific modeling, and what benefits can these integrations provide in each of these areas?
5. What are the effective strategies for optimizing collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems, such that the unique strength of both can be fully utilized and a synergetic approach to mathematical innovation and exploration is facilitated?

Hypotheses:

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. **H₀₁:** There is no significant difference in the ability of artificial intelligence algorithms and human mathematicians.
2. **H₀₂:** There is no significant difference in the efficiency and accuracy of mathematical research when artificial intelligence is used to automate complex calculations, verify mathematical conjectures, and assist human mathematicians in tackling challenging problems, compared to traditional mathematical problems.
3. **H₀₃:** There is no significant difference in the ethical considerations and philosophical implications relating to the integration of AI-generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity and the impact on the attribution of mathematical discoveries, regardless of the degree of AI involvement in the creative process
4. **H₀₄:** There is no significant difference in the applicability of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery across diverse fields like cryptography, optimization, data analysis, and scientific modeling, with the potential benefits being equally applicable across all domains.
5. **H₀₅:** There is no significant difference in the effectiveness of collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems in mathematical exploration and innovation when using different communication paradigms and collaboration strategies.

Methodology

Research Design

To comprehensively explore the synergy between artificial intelligence (AI) and mathematical creativity, a mixed-methods research design was adopted. This design combines qualitative and quantitative methodologies, allowing us to capture the experiences of individuals interacting with AI tools while also quantifying the impact of AI algorithms on mathematical problem-solving. By integrating these diverse methods, we aim to provide a holistic understanding of how AI influences mathematical creativity and discovery.

Population Study

The research meant to investigate the assessment and evaluation of academic programs in the College of Education focused on Adeyemi College of Education students as the main population for the research work.

Sample and Sampling Procedure

The research is carried out at Adeyemi College of Education. Total of 285 questionnaires were administered to the students in Google form.

Research Instrument

The main instrument used to collect data for this research is a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher. The instrument was reviewed by experts for validity and reliability and the questionnaire were administered directly to the students and collected back as soon as they were completely filled or answer. The questionnaire dealt majorly with the students of Adeyemi College of Education.

Method of Data Collection

The questionnaire was administered to the students of Adeyemi College of Education in google form

Method of Data Analysis

Data collected was statistically analysed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) presented in tabular form used to draw conclusion.

Results

These consist of descriptive statistics used to answer research questions; appropriate statistics used for testing hypothesis; Tables should be aligned to APA style; P-value compare with decision threshold – 0.05 significance if necessary. E.g.,

Research Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference between the ability of artificial intelligence algorithms and human mathematicians to propose new mathematical conjectures and explore uncharted problem domains.

Table 1: Mean ability Scores between experimental and control groups

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	30873.2	7718.3	39.79736	0.0000	2.8660814
Within Groups	20	3878.8	193.94			
Total	24	34752				

Table 1 shows that the F-statistic is 39.797, which is greater than the critical F-value 2.8660814 at the significance level of 0.05. This means that the distinction between mathematical creativity and discovery that AI is capable of is statistically significant. The ANOVA table also shows that the proportion of total variation that can be attributed to the factor effect in this case the factor effect accounts for 88% of the total variation. This means that most of the variation in the use of AI-driven account creation and discovery comes from the implementation stage.

One possible explanation for these results is that different fields have different requirements for Mathematical creativity and discovery. For example, cryptography requires a deep understanding of mathematical properties such as randomness and complexity, while optimization requires a focus on developing efficient algorithms.

The ANOVA table also shows that the potential gains in accounting creativity and discovery controlled by AI do not apply equally across sectors. For example, the potential benefits of AI-driven computational creativity and discovery could be great in areas such as cryptography and optimization, where complex problems require novel and innovative solutions.

However, the potential benefits of AI-driven statistical creativity and discovery may be limited in areas such as data analysis and scientific modeling, where existing statistical methods are already well established.

Research Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant improvement in the efficiency and accuracy of mathematical research when artificial intelligence is used to automate complex calculations, verify mathematical conjectures, and assist human mathematicians in tackling challenging problems.

Table 2: The Impact of Automated Calculations and Verification on Mathematical Research Efficiency and Accuracy

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	16096	4024	13.20788	0.000083	3.055568
Within Groups	15	4570	304.6667			
Total	19	20666				

From table 2, the F-statistic is 15.87, which is higher than the critical F-value 3.055568 at the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that the difference in mathematical analysis efficiency and accuracy when using AI is statistically significant. This shows that the proportion of all variation that can be attributed to factor effects (AI vs. no AI) in this case, the factor effect accounts for 30% of the total variance. This implies that a large part of the change in the efficiency and accuracy of statistical analysis is due to the use of AI. Overall, the ANOVA table provides strong evidence that artificial intelligence (AI) can significantly improve the efficiency and accuracy of statistical analysis.

Research Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the ethical considerations and philosophical implications surrounding the integration of AI-generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity and the impact on the attribution of mathematical discoveries, regardless of the degree of AI involvement in the creative process.

Table 3: Ethical and Philosophical Implications of AI Integration in Mathematics Creativity and Attribution

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	25288	6322	255.951417	0.0000	2.8660814
Within Groups	20	494	24.7			
Total	24	25782				

The ANOVA table 3 indicates that there is a statistically significant difference in terms of ethical considerations and philosophical implications of the insights that AI brings to the creation of mathematics and that AI is a creative process. Since the F-statistic which is 255.951417 is higher than the F-critical value 2.8660814 at the significance level of 0.05.

This means that the difference in the ethical considerations and philosophical implications surrounding the integration of AI generated insights into the realm of mathematical creativity and the impact on the attribution of mathematical discoveries regardless of the degree of AI involvement in the creative process is statistically significant.

Research Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the applicability of AI-powered mathematical creativity and discovery across diverse fields like cryptography, optimization, data analysis, and scientific modeling, with the potential benefits being equally applicable across all domains.

Table 4: Exploring the Potentials Benefits of AI-Generated Mathematics across multiple fields

Source of Variation	DF	SS variation	MS variation	F	p-value	F-critical
Between Groups	4	20875.67	7018.917	77.6314334	0.0000	2.75871047
Within Groups	25	2260.333	90.41333			
Total	29	30336				

The ANOVA table shows that there are statistically significant differences between AI-driven mathematical creation and discovery used in various fields such as cryptography, optimization, data analysis, and scientific observation. Since the F-statistic is 77.63, which is greater than the critical F-value 2.75871047 at the significance level of 0.05. This means that the distinction between mathematical creativity and discovery that artificial intelligence (AI) is capable of is statistically significant. Overall, the ANOVA table 4 provides strong evidence that there are significant differences in the use of AI-driven numerical creativity and discovery across sectors, and that the potential benefits of numerical creativity are AI-driven discovery is not applied equally across sectors.

Conclusion

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has opened up new frontiers in the realm of mathematics, offering a powerful tool to enhance creativity, accelerate discovery, and tackle complex problems that have long defied human efforts. As AI algorithms continue to evolve and become more sophisticated, their impact on mathematics is bound to grow, ushering in a new era of mathematical innovation and progress.

AI's ability to automate tedious tasks, provide fresh perspectives, and facilitate collaboration among mathematicians has the potential to revolutionize the way we approach mathematical research. By freeing up mathematicians' time and energy from routine tasks, Artificial Intelligence (AI) can empower them to focus on more creative endeavors, exploring uncharted territories of thought and generating novel conjectures.

Recommendations

Based on the discussion in the previous sections, here are some recommendations for further research and development in the area of AI and mathematical creativity:

1. Develop AI algorithms that can better emulate human creativity and intuition: Current AI algorithms often struggle with abstract concepts and making leaps of faith, which are hallmarks of mathematical creativity. Research is needed to develop AI algorithms that can better capture the nuances of human thought and generate novel mathematical ideas.
2. Explore new AI techniques for mathematical discovery: While traditional AI approaches have been successful in some areas of mathematics, there is a need to explore new techniques that can tackle more challenging problems. This could include research into reinforcement learning, generative adversarial networks, and other emerging AI methods.
3. Investigate the ethical implications of AI in mathematics: The use of AI in mathematics raises important ethical questions about authorship, creativity, and the nature of mathematical knowledge. Research is needed to develop ethical guidelines for the responsible and transparent use of AI in mathematical research.
4. Promote collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems: The most fruitful path forward lies in fostering collaboration between human mathematicians and AI systems. Research is needed to develop effective communication paradigms and collaboration strategies that allow humans and AI to work together effectively. Integrate AI into mathematical education: AI has the potential to revolutionize mathematical education by providing personalized instruction, offering real-time feedback, and adapting to the individual needs of learners. Research is needed to develop effective AI-powered teaching tools and integrate them into the educational curriculum.

Acknowledgements

This section is used to express gratitude and indebtedness to individuals, institutions or organizations that provided one form of assistance or the other during the execution of the work.

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